

Transcription of the Focus Group "Unlocking Potentials of Green Coding into Practice" – Workshop at EnviroInfo 2024 in Cairo

Focus Group Topic 2 - "Opportunities and Challenges of Integrating Green Coding Methods in Software Engineering Processes"

[Speaker 1]

Thank you. Thank you very much. Another question from the time box.

Five minutes for this question. It's nearly over. Any input?

So we now go to the next three questions. The next three time boxes. It's now more about opportunities and challenges of integrating green coding methods in the software engineering process.

And as you maybe heard this morning when I was talking about our structured expert interview at EcoCompute, we were focused about young professionals and the problems they will have in their career or in the starting of their career. But today we will talk more about the general transfer into practice, what the opportunities and problems are when integrating it into the process. Can you please jump on the next slide?

And so the question for you is what are the main challenges that companies face when integrating green coding practices into existing software development processes? And what strategies can be used to overcome these obstacles? So as we see, it's always going about obstacles.

Anyone has a feeling about that he or she can contribute to these obstacles or how to overcome it?

[Speaker 6]

Yeah, maybe your question was about data centers or about the energy consumption of data centers. And I think an approach or a challenge is that you need to integrate maybe green IT itself in the software development process or the software developers need to know about the inefficient data center because I think it's not very known that servers are idling so much in the data center industry and there are big efficiencies you could do.

[Speaker 1]

So when I understand it right, it was a lot about awareness that they have to think about it to integrate it.

[Speaker 11]

To use your idea, with the awareness, maybe a gamification would be a strategy because programmers mostly are gamers and they want to compete each other and they have an algorithm that is 1% better. So make a challenge out of it.

[Speaker 1]

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Make a high score board, a blackboard and have it more transparent.

[Speaker 7]

I think developers love tools and need tools. We have seen in one talk that the co-pilot could reduce energy consumption. We have in other talks learned that special data calls or statements create energy consumption.

So there could be tools that use this information about other functions and then generate other functions that are less energy consuming. So I think tooling is a good one approach to reduce energy consumption and to provide green coping practices.

[Speaker 1]

Thank you. I think we lost the second microphone.

[Speaker 2]

So here from an academic perspective, first, so academically, we teach software engineering, DevOps, things like this. I think this topic needs to be integrated in the curriculum. We don't have green coding in the DevOps or the software engineering in our university.

I don't know about Birchland or Poland or wherever you are from. I don't know what they do actually. Do they teach green coding as part of DevOps or software engineering?

If this is not the case, then we as academic people need to incorporate this in the software engineering somehow or DevOps courses we teach master's students and so on. Practitioning-wise, or I was in the industry before my PhD, so I think that we will be reluctant to train our own models. So we need to have pre-trained models.

So when you publish your work, it would be great if you publish it on some place we can download your model. So there are certain machine learning as a service services or like AI as a service websites. So please publish your models there so we can reuse it because maybe we don't have the capacity to train our own models to classify maybe the code or the software or our tools.

So it would be a nice idea that if we have a hub, some kind of AI or machine learning as a service hub that already all these models from this field are collected there, pre-trained, all you have to do is plug and play. Here you go. There's the model and plug it in and then try to assess what's going on in your software.

[Speaker 1]

Maybe also have already an KPI about the effectiveness or the greenishness of the model so you can choose wise later.

[Speaker 2]

Yeah.

[Speaker 4]

I think that's like- Like hugging face. You know, hugging face.

[Speaker 2]

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Yeah. Something like hugging face but for this stuff.

[Speaker 4]

I think that specifically AI has one of the challenges with it is that you have the upfront cost of training but that also brings with it the opportunity of increased recyclability of code. So if you have really good pre-trained models, you can reuse them to great effect and that may bring about great effects when you scale it. A lot of people are using the model but it doesn't need to be retrained that often.

[Speaker 3]

I also agree that knowledge and tooling are important points because my impression is that there is quite some knowledge on green coding but it's not easily accessible in one place. You might want to look. I think from the web standards for web development, they provide also guidelines on green web development and this website is actually quite nice because you get different categories where you can do something about making your code more green and it's easily accessible in one place.

All the information is collected which makes it easier. And then tooling. Developers love tools.

I agree. So I think ideally it would be ideal to have something like the performance tools where you get feedback in the IDE while developing your code. You get feedback on how green your code is and maybe even recommendations how you could improve your code and make it more.

Yeah, measurements or if it's not possible. I mean, there's also a lot of research and also what I'm looking at more or less that you research on different programming concepts how much energy they use and then relatively, I don't know, this one data structure consumes more energy than the other but they fulfill the same purpose so you could just give recommendations and maybe look into this data structure. It's more energy efficient.

Yet the developer has to decide because it depends a lot on the context whether it's possible for them to use the more energy efficient alternative.

[Speaker 4]

But that will maybe go in the direction of creating a reputable body of knowledge when it comes to green coding practices.

[Speaker 7]

Yeah, tooling and knowledge creation. That's the point I wanted to add. When talking about tooling, it's not only the development process but also the design process.

So maybe we can develop tools that measure the energy consumption of a software architecture and provide hints what to do better. And when we talk about body of knowledge, maybe we can create something like energy-safe by design. We have privacy by design so maybe low energy consumption by design.

And then we have this concept of design patterns. So design patterns provide a solution to a problem. So maybe we can develop design patterns to solve several energy consumption problems that occur again and again.

So I think this knowledge creation process should be more conceptualized to provide knowledge that we can provide other people.

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[Speaker 3]

There's also already some research about sustainable design patterns.

[Speaker 10]

Thank you.

[Speaker 9]

Another point that I can see here is focus on companies. And what I can see from companies is that they are focused on value creation. Now they're focused on, let's invest in AI, IT, and so on.

And they don't focus on the sustainability side. They just want to get the revenue fast. So maybe starting here from the strategy, but they like this strategy and then that can focus on this green coding and this sustainability practices.

[Speaker 1]

So it's going in the direction of soft skills creating value in a change management process. And maybe I'll tell the employee about how we create value and why this is beneficial for the company.

[Speaker 9]

Exactly, but maybe not only telling, also making it part of the strategy. You should do it, you must do it. Not just as a recommendation, but it will be nice if you do it.

[Speaker 4]

I think one of the ideas around this is that sustainability should be a functional requirement in software processes. Is that what you would agree with?

[Speaker 9]

Exactly, being part of the requirements in engineering of this software development process. Thank you.

[Speaker 1]

Thank you. I think this time box of five minutes is going to the end. I have a little vote for you.

What should they focus for? Like soft skills, change management, measurement? So it's also a minimum of tools for measure or generally software engineering process information.

You can vote multiple times. I will speak it into the microphone so we can record it and transcribe it later. Who thinks soft skills for this change management process are important?

There need to be more KPIs. It has to be visualized for everyone what they do. For example, when we were talking about the bow agent, it was integrated into the Promo Toys software with Promo Toys and the Grafana dashboard.

So the developer or also the management can see this KPIs, if it's getting better or worse. So like information about the process itself.

[Speaker 4]

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I think like some examples of this would be there's a green software engineering model which supplies some artifacts that might be used in scrum or traditional development processes, such as like a sustainability journal or a sustainability introspection. So providing just the engineering tools. There's also some literature, I think also by Patricia Lago or by Birgit Penzelstadler about green software requirements engineering.

I would put that under this third point.

[Speaker 1]

So then I would say, let's start the vote. Who thinks soft skills and change management should be focused on for this change? I see one hand for the record.

Then who votes for tools, measurements? One, two, three, four, five. Five hands are there.

And the third one, software engineering process information. One, two, three, four, five, six, seven. Okay, again, one, two, three, four, five, six.

Yeah, it's seven. Good, thank you for that. Let's go to the fifth question.

The fifth question is, how can training programs can be designed to address the specific needs and challenges faced by different roles in software engineering? For example, developers, project managers, quality assurance engineers, all from different roles that people have to work with each other. And we want to create the training.

This is the goal of the research project. What would be the best format?

[Speaker 4]

So maybe a good starting point for this one would be imagine you're in a room and you are supposed to learn about green coding. Would you prefer maybe like just a general preference on how you like to learn? But how would you, if you had to take a course on this, how would you like to approach it?

[Speaker 5]

I think it's a cultural thing. So it would be best if you have a real face-to-face training so that everyone speaks on the same language, so that everyone knows, okay, we are for green coding and not just doing online tests, for example. This is just like clicking through slides and then, okay, I've done it, but I don't feel it maybe.

So it would be always the best if you feel it and you make this happen when you just talk face-to-face with people and doing a workshop, maybe not just one hour, maybe a little bit longer so that everyone gets a feeling and can also talk about their anxiety or something else. This would be best, in my opinion.

[Speaker 1]

So we should have to go, for example, into a company and start to sensitize them, create awareness?

[Speaker 5]

Yes, because when you just have someone at the top of the board, maybe, and he's not convinced, then everything you can do is maybe not okay. So you have to convince everyone. This is only good when you just do a training for everyone and face-to-face would be nice.

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[Speaker 10]

Thank you. Yeah. How would...

Yeah, please.

[Speaker 3]

So I also think that in person might be the best way because you have a better chance to convey the importance of the topic to the people and motivate them. But I also think that certificates are good. People like certificates, so I would do a test with a certificate in the end as well.

[Speaker 6]

Yeah, maybe you would need also more conferences. You mentioned the EcoCompute. Maybe this is also the best way how to share knowledge and how to share methods and so on in a very fancy way having a conference.

[Speaker 1]

Yeah, I think this is a good point. You can put it in the conference. So if we don't forget it until we vote, we should put a four-point here for vote later.

It's for conferences and gatherings maybe. It's the focus.

[Speaker 10]

Any more ideas? Thank you.

[Speaker 8]

I do believe in-house training would be the best way simply because... My reason for it would be that surrounding yourself with like-minded people is really effective when it comes to the process of learning. You may achieve this, of course, with an online course, but not everyone may have studied for this point.

So yeah, in-house training would be... It's the most awesome way of introducing the idea and living through it and just discussing it all together. It's a good experience.

Thank you.

[Speaker 2]

For me as well, for the university, I think we need to provide electives outside the Umweltinformatics world. So we are a business informatics world. Why don't you provide us electives?

Provide us an elective about this course. Maybe a green coding course or something. And then this would be an optional course for someone in order to graduate they need to study an elective and this can be one of the electives.

For the companies, I would agree with Anne that they need certificates. If you wish to enhance your CV maybe if this green coding has a standard kind of certification then the people start seeking it and then the recruitment. The companies need to care about it.

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The challenge is how to make the companies actually focus on the CVs for the interviews to the ones that have the green coding certification. How can we motivate the recruiters that you need to think about this that this person has green coding skills and this is the right candidate instead of this other one because they don't have this certificate. So this is the challenge.

I don't know how to fix that but I mean if you have a certification that's the starting point. If we make a certification program then you can become a certified green coder or something like this. Nice title.

Sounds good. And then maybe the recruiters need to be motivated to focus on the CV. Take this candidate and things like that.

[Speaker 1]

So it's also good for the motivation to have a certificate in the end so you maybe study it and not just passively listen to the online course or the in-house training because you have to do it and it's doing working hours so you need to motivate the patient. So thank you for that and now let's do this vote again. Again multiple votes are allowed.

The four questions are webinar, online course, in-house training, online test with certificate and conferences or gatherings. Let's start with the format. What's prepared?

The webinar, the online course. Who will vote for that? One, two.

Two hands up. We go on in-house training.

[Speaker 10]

It's seven or eight.

[Speaker 1]

Are you voting? So it's seven. Then we go on online test with certificates or let's change it to certificates at all.

It's three hands up and the fourth point was conferences and gatherings.

[Speaker 10]

Five hands up.

[Speaker 1]

Six hands. Perfect. Now we head on to the last question.

How can green coding training can be integrated into existing technical training programs without overwhelming developers with additional requirements? How can we make sure that green coding content stays up to date? So of course if there's new ideas and you overwhelm them and you put too much barriers on it, the people will not follow the paths you give them.

So how we can do it easily? So maybe slip it in into normal trainings or maybe if there's a computer engineering training or server training, server administration training, how can we put it in? And do you have any ideas how we can make sure that the green coding content stays up to date?

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So sometimes courses are created and the same course, the same lecture is used 20 years, 14 semesters, you all know it. And how we can do it that it stays up to date and it's not like that.

[Speaker 10]

Yes.

[Speaker 5]

Maybe putting this into conferences like this. So having the up-to-date research about green coding on conferences and make it more not even just like two tracks, but maybe even one day green coding for specialists that they can exchange and get in touch maybe from other companies or from other research institutes that they can meet up and then exchange information and talk to each other.

[Speaker 10]

Thank you. Any more inputs?

[Speaker 8]

One thing I'm thinking of is that there would be a way to integrate green coding patterns, green coding philosophy and things like that into existing frameworks that people already take like a study. This would allow them to be compelled to write code in a certain way. They would be compelled to think in a certain way that aligns with green coding and of course by updating the framework, because it's still widely used, the developers would have to learn it and it just stays always an active development and active learning.

[Speaker 10]

Thank you. Any more ideas?

[Speaker 1]

Inputs?

[Speaker 6]

Well, maybe you would need some really catchy examples for developers. You need to know why you need to put some effort into this topic of green coding and software has a large scaling effect. I think it's important specifically to know for developers why should I do this?

Why should I do green coding methods, green coding software engineering?

[Speaker 1]

If they're aware then the training can be integrated everywhere and they maybe will find the material by themselves. Or how can I understand it? Yes, kind of, yeah.

So, any more ideas? I think the time box of the whole workshop is going to the end, even if we didn't reach the five minutes of this question. If nobody has an idea, I would say, yeah, let's do again the little vote.

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I have after every question I present that. So, what fitting integration forms could be? We have the standalone training option, integration, full integration option, others, like just create awareness and let's do them by themselves, or both or all options.

And now this is now like with both, all, yeah, but we can multiple vote, so we can really try that this voting in the end will be a mess. So, let's start with the standalone trainings. Who will vote for standalone trainings?

It's three hands up. Then let's go for the full integration into courses. It's one.

Four hands up. Then other options.

[Speaker 10]

Nobody. And both or all. It's six hands up.

So, let's move on to the last slide.

[Speaker 1]

Thank you for participating. Thank you for conducting this expert interview with us. Thank you very much.

And I think now after this workshop, we all need a little break. And then we can gather outside for looking at a petrified forest. Thank you.

[Speaker 10]

Thank you all.